

A web-based property management catalogue system for St. Dominic College of Asia

Justin Q. Pagunsan*, Mat. Jerico A. Sergio, Akinori K. Caro, James Kyle F. Esguerra,
Mary Grace S. Jamir
Information Technology Department, School of Business and Computer Studies, St. Dominic College of
Asia, Bacoar City, Cavite, Philippines
*Corresponding author

Abstract

A web-based system that assists companies in managing their inventory and tracking their assets is the web-based property management catalogue system. Using a centralized platform that can be accessed from any device with an internet connection, the system enables users to manage their inventory. Businesses may easily make informed decisions regarding their inventory and sales strategy because to the system's real-time updates on inventory levels, sales, and other crucial information. The department's institution is facing difficulties as they lack an efficient system to manage their inventory and requisition data. The Property Management Office's current process for issuing forms and managing inventory using Excel is also manual. Maintaining stocks is crucial due to unpredictable changes in product supply and demand and serves as a safeguard against future price fluctuations. The analysis' main objective is to examine the efficiency of the inventory management system, including a review of the existing system. The study also looks at how inventory levels and reports are affected by changes in stock prices. The study used Agile methodology to develop an ISO 9126-compliant web-based property management catalogue system for a client. The System was evaluated using ISO 9126, and participants in the study were selected using simple random probability sampling. The client can request unused inventory and claim approved unused inventory on material requisition slips. Using a five-point Likert scale, the system's functionality, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability were evaluated by 50 respondents comprising 80% end-users and 20% expert users. The results indicated very acceptable scores for functionality, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability, respectively. The overall rating of 1.48 suggests that the system meets clients' expectations and is feasible and acceptable, requiring a mean rating of 2.51 or lower.

Keywords: *Web-based inventory management system; Material requisition system; Inventory system; Catalogue system; Inventories.*

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Introduction

Before the Industrial Revolution, shopkeepers were generally obliged to list every product sold every day. Products were ordered based on the handwritten documents. The manner of operating is utterly erroneous and ineffective. Without routinely performing time-consuming physical counts, which appear to be more laborious, and could not account for stolen products. Due to poor keeping the record, it also had trouble ensuring that the received of correct quantity of goods when orders came in. As a result, a plan was developed to look for more efficient ways to manage stock, including one that tries to envision how a computer would read punch cards and transmit data to the storeroom (Oluwole, 2019).

Manual inventory management has many drawbacks. Processing orders from each sales channel separately and carrying out regular manual stock checks so you can adjust your stock levels on each platform takes a lot of time. Furthermore, that time would be better spent growing your business. A lack of real-time stock level visibility and delays in placing orders when stock levels are low, stockouts, and lost can all result from the time it takes to reconcile this information (Syed, 2021).

Ensuring timely delivery of your products to customers forms the lifeblood of your business. Efficiently managing and staying in control of your inventory enables you to meet customer demand and generate sales successfully. The lifeblood of your business is getting your products to your customers on time. Staying on top of your inventory and managing it efficiently helps you meet demand and generate sales (Jenkins, 2022). Managing inventory is extremely critical for business growth (Gao et al., 2022). Through the internet, information technology enables human to accomplish anything. In this instance, the company needs information technology solutions to significantly impact how well it develops its business (Utami & Yulianto, 2019).

The inventory system is designed to be capable of meeting intended consumer demand. Inventory is designed to keep customers delighted in addition to assisting in the separation of various aspects or components of the production process. It is now possible to avoid problems brought on by swings because there is more inventory to keep the production operations process and suppliers separate. Managing an entire business is a difficult endeavor, especially if done alone. Accepting deliveries from the supplier, listing the supplied items, setting the items up on the shelves, and carrying out several additional jobs are all required. Nevertheless, a person will probably become perplexed, particularly if the customer and supplier arrive at the same time. They manually store data, accounts, and transactions to manage the sales and inventory, which causes unamortized expenses. This can determine the advantages a business is handling by utilizing this modernized web-based property management system. Time savings come first. The largest advantage of employing a computerized inventory system may be the time that an institution might save (Soegoto & Palalungan, 2020).

Singh and Gameti (2021) stated that an official order used to notify department managers or purchasing officials about a decision to make a purchase is called a purchase requisition. The purchasing department will create a purchase order and send it to the supplier following the submission of a purchase requisition (and approval of the purchase). This legally-binding document specifies every item the company plans to buy. A purchase request form is one of the internal documents utilized by departments when they make a purchase. By using this form, the department can provide the purchasing department with crucial purchasing data so that they can place precise purchases on behalf of the rest of the company. The PMS, or purchasing management system, offers a centralized computer system is utilized to plan, arrange, and execute routine tasks and transactions necessary in diverse businesses. By facilitating updates and centralized access to records from multiple computers and devices, computerized record-keeping and PMS (Property Management System) solutions have significantly enhanced company efficiency. To cater to the requirements of different industries, PMS solutions have been adapted and refined to enhance operational ease-of-use even further.

The material requisition system helps to ensure that materials are procured in an organized and efficient manner, and that there is adequate oversight and control over the purchasing process (Afolabi et al., 2020). This can help to prevent waste, fraud, abuse, and ensure that materials are used effectively to support the organization's goals and objectives.

Objectives

The study aims to create a web-based property management catalog system for St. Dominic College of Asia's Property Management Office that streamline the inventory management, simplify purchasing, and improve overall business operations at the same time address the issues on requisition tracking, payment management, inventory monitoring, and report generation by providing effective and

efficient the system's functionality, security that impact on institutional cost; saving performance. Specifically, it aims to:

- Analyze and plan the system to understand the step by step process of business and determine precisely and concretely the needs of the client.
- Design and develop user-friendly material procurement system by providing module for request and approval of inventory goods, an inventory module for real-time stock monitoring as well as the availability of low stock alerts, and a report generation module with analytics to facilitate strategic decisions regarding purchasing, supply chain management, and cost-cutting.
- Evaluate system functionality, security, and scalability, and assess the impact on institutional performance in terms of inventory data accuracy, procurement costs, and user satisfaction.
- Implement a secure user login module with specific user roles and limited permissions to protect data privacy and maintain the system, including bug-free operation, and manage inventory records to ensure resource availability and prevent delays.

Methodology

System Development Approach

Figure 1. Agile System Development Life Cycle

The System Development Life Cycle, or SDLC, was used as the methodology for the design and development of the system. A method for organizing and processing the system is the SDLC. It facilitates the planning of software development, offering a well-organized flow of stages that arrange to swiftly build high-quality software, allowing efficiency in the time to create (Stackify Team, 2020), is a conceptual framework that describes all of the tasks involved in developing software, from planning through maintenance (de Vicente Mohino et al., 2019). The Agile methodology was applied when the programmers added a feature to the DOSE system used by St. Dominic College of Asia. The Agile SDLC technique is a way to structure a project by breaking it down into many stages (Edeki, 2015). Agile refers to methods for developing software that incorporates ongoing planning, learning, and improvement, teamwork, evolutionary development, and early delivery (Wilson, 2022). The programmers used the Agile Methodology to make plans on creating the system each member has their own roles to fulfill, as this will help to speed up the development of the research and system. Agile SDLC relies on iterative, cycle-based development of working software and collaborative decision-making amongst teams working on

requirements and solutions. As the programmers integrate the project into the school's Dominican One Stop Enrollment (DOSE) system, this model will be utilized to direct system planning.

Analysis. To plan the System, the first step is to analyze the system. The researcher must understand the step-by-step process of the business-related information on which the system will be based, as well as how the system can accommodate the needs and efficiency of the user.

Planning. Creating a plan can assist in making the researcher's objectives more distinct; it aids in determining precisely and concretely what needs to be done to influence the system. Involving everyone in the planning process helps the researcher comprehend the objective and what is required to achieve it.

Design. It is designed to meet the needs for the PMO and the other department staff users who will be using the System. It is a simple design that is easy to understand and user friendly.

Development. After planning and designing the system, the programmers can start developing the system by each module on the system.

Testing. Testing will help us give more feedback to the user whether it is useful to them or efficient on their daily tasks, it also helps us see if the system has errors and bugs to the system and if the user does not want a certain feature to be implemented

Implement. Implementing the system to tailor the needs of the users adding new features if any new requests on the system to further improve it in the long run.

Maintenance. Keeping the system in check and maintaining it to avoid bugs or errors on the system when implementing new features to the system and maintaining the health of the database's data, since too much information in a database can cause system lag, are examples of system maintenance.

Data Modules

Inventory. Monitoring of inventories and logs of add and update, and printing list of inventory and reports. It has notifications for depleted quantities of inventory. This module provides monitoring for inventory stocks, including adding, updating, and discarding of insignificant inventories.

Issuance. The Issuance module allows users to view every client request. Each transaction will be authorized by the Budget Officer before being forwarded to the PMO. Monitoring issuance, receiving reports, a list of requests, and a form for requesting materials or purchases are all part of the system.

Technical Feasibility

The programming languages that were used to build the system were JavaScript, PHP, HTML and CodeIgniter as a development web framework, for use in building dynamic web sites with PHP. For web-based system development, the developers used MySQL, Codeigniter, Xampp, HeidiSQL, GitHub and Visual Studio, as this will help in building and designing the website as well as providing a server database to store the data. The minimum requirements for hardware to run the web system consist of an Intel i3 or AMD A8 processor or higher, 4 GB of RAM or above, a hard drive, and at least an Intel HD 3000 or higher graphics card.

Level of Satisfaction

The researchers utilized a survey questionnaire with a five-point Likert Scale, from Strongly Disagree to Strongly Agree, to properly evaluate the application's level of satisfaction in terms of

functionality, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability based on the respondents' evaluation and feedback.

Table 1. Level of Satisfaction

Scale	Numerical Scale	Descriptive Rating
1	1.0 - 1.50	Highly Acceptable
2	1.51 - 2.50	Very Acceptable
3	2.51 - 3.50	Acceptable
4	3.51 - 4.50	Fairly Acceptable
5	4.51 - 5.00	Not Acceptable

Table 1 shows the scale to interpret the total mean based on the respondent's responses. The numerical scale indicates the level of satisfaction from highly acceptable to not acceptable. That said, the overall rating of the Web Based Property Management Catalogue is anticipated to be 2.51 or lower for the researchers to conclude that the project is feasible and acceptable.

Data Analysis

The respondents for the web-based property management catalogue are head department assistants, employees from St. Dominic College of Asia, the ICT Department, and other professionals from the IT industry. Fifty (50) respondents participated in the project. There are 80% of end-users (n=40) and 20% of experts (n=10), totaling 100 percent. The table indicates that most respondents are end-users. The expected number of respondents from the departments of St. Dominic College of Asia was not achieved due to time constraints during the system evaluation process.

Conducting the evaluation typically takes 45 minutes to one hour, and researchers prioritized showing the clients the system's design and function before allowing them to test it as part of training. Based on feedback from clients who have tested the system, they recommend implementing certain functions that are currently lacking, as well as incorporating features that is received with praise for their effectiveness. These changes will help improve the overall user experience of the web system. The mean is the sum of all the scores divided by the number of respondents. After the evaluation, the data collected were tallied and analyzed. The mean (X) describes the validity of the respondents' responses.

Results and Discussion

Table 2. Evaluation of the web system's functionality

End Users (n=40)			Expert Users (n=10)		
Functionality	Mean	Remarks	Functionality	Mean	Remarks
Suitability. The application's functionalities input accordingly.	1.41	Highly Acceptable	Suitability. The web system allows you to record prices, request material inventory, and accept items.	1.30	Highly Acceptable
Accurateness. The information that the inventory prices, quantity and availability presented is accurate.	1.41	Highly Acceptable	Accurateness. The algorithms used for calculating prices, stocks, and availability are accurate.	1.50	Very Acceptable
Security. The user can only access certain functions that are assigned to that role.	1.38	Highly Acceptable	Security. The access of users per module is applicable and functional.	1.50	Very Acceptable
Overall Average	1.40	Highly Acceptable		1.44	Highly Acceptable

Table 2 shows the evaluation of the web system's functionality. Based on the end users' evaluation, the functionality of the web system received a highly acceptable rating of 1.40. The system's suitability, accurateness, and security were all highly rated, indicating that it can accurately process user

inputs, present accurate inventory information, and provide secure access control for users based on their assigned roles. Overall, the system appears to be highly functional and effective for managing material requisitions. Therefore, it is recommended to continue gathering feedback and making necessary improvements to ensure the system's functionality aligns with the stakeholders' requirements.

The web system received a highly acceptable rating in terms of functionality with 1.44 for expert users. The first criterion, Suitability, indicates that the system allows for these functionalities, resulting in a score of 1.30, which is rated as "Highly Acceptable." The second criterion, Accurateness, indicates that the system's algorithms are accurate, resulting in a score of 1.50, which is rated as "Very Acceptable." The third criterion, Security, states that the system's access for users per module is applicable and functional, resulting in a score of 1.50, which is also rated as "Very Acceptable." This indicates that the web system is highly functional and provides a positive user experience. Overall, the system's functionalities are accurate and secure, while also meeting the needs of its users.

Table 3. Evaluation of the web system's usability

End Users (n=40)			Expert Users (n=10)		
Usability	Mean	Remarks	Usability	Mean	Remarks
Understandability. The web system is easy to understand.	1.38	Highly Acceptable	Understandability. The web system's material requisition is able to fill out for requesting of items, and the labels that the user input element is clear and understandable.	1.5	Very Acceptable
Learnability. The use of the web system and items in material requisition slip is clear.	1.41	Highly Acceptable	Learnability. Requesting of items is used easily without instructions.	1.58	Very Acceptable
Operability. The web system meets user requirements efficiently and correct.	1.43	Highly Acceptable	Operability. The web system handles user input efficiently.	1.33	Highly Acceptable
Overall Average	1.41	Highly Acceptable		1.47	Highly Acceptable

Table 3 reveals the evaluation of the web system's usability. Based on the end users' evaluation of the material requisition system on the client side, the system has a very acceptable level of usability with an overall average of 1.41. The users find the web system's Material Requisition Slip easy to fill up and understand, and they can use the system efficiently without the need for instructions. The operability of the web system also meets the users' requirements efficiently and accurately. Overall, the users have provided a positive evaluation of the material requisition system's usability. This suggests that the system is user-friendly and easy to navigate, and users can perform their tasks efficiently and effectively. Further evaluation and feedback from users in different roles may be necessary to fully assess the system's usability.

The expert-users' evaluation of the application's usability received a highly acceptable rating of 1.47. The expert user finds the web system's how easily a user can comprehend and interpret the labels and instructions provided by the web system. It is easy to fill out, and the labels provided for each user input element are clear and understandable. The score for this criterion is 1.5, which means that the system is rated as "Very Acceptable" in terms of understandability. The operability of the web system is also able to handle user input and is evaluated as highly acceptable. Overall, the respondents have provided a positive evaluation of the material requisition system's usability. This suggests that the system is user-friendly and easy to learn and understand, and the system can perform their task successfully. It also indicates that the system's design and interface are simple and easy to understand to the user's standards.

Table 4. Evaluation of the web system's efficiency

End Users (n=40)			Expert Users (n=10)		
Efficiency	Mean	Remarks	Efficiency	Mean	Remarks
Time behavior. The web system loads timely (e.g., reloading web portal requisition, checking of inventory and present requisitions).	1.41	Highly Acceptable	Time behavior. The web system loads efficient actions (e.g. submit button, re pages, submission of requisition, and uploading data)	1.58	Very Acceptable
Resource utilization. The service of the web manages its resources and meet the user requirements.	1.53	Very Acceptable	Resource Utilization. The web system's services provide efficiency to its resources..	1.41	Highly Acceptable
Effectiveness. The web system is capable of making requisitions.	1.46	Highly Acceptable	Effectiveness. Each of the web system's modules achieve its objectives (e.g., Material requisition, Issuance)	1.41	Highly Acceptable
Overall Average	1.47	Highly Acceptable		1.47	Highly Acceptable

Table 4 indicates the evaluation of the web system's efficiency. The end users' evaluation of the application's efficiency received a highly acceptable rating of 1.47. Users find the web system easy to understand and use without instructions, while meeting their requirements efficiently and correctly. The system also loads quickly after actions have been taken and provides efficient use of their resources. The system's high level of efficiency helps users to accomplish their tasks more effectively, which in turn increases the productivity of the organization.

The expert-user evaluation of the application's efficiency received a highly acceptable rating of 1.47 in terms of its efficiency on timely functions and resource utilization. The first criterion, time behavior, indicates that the system loads efficiently, resulting in a score of 1.58, which is rated as "Very Acceptable." The second criterion, resource utilization, states that the system's services are able to provide efficiency, resulting in a score of 1.41, which is rated as "Highly Acceptable." The third criterion, effectiveness, indicates that each module is capable of achieving its objectives, resulting in a score of 1.41, which is also rated as "Highly Acceptable." Finally, the overall average score is 1.47, which is rated as "Highly Acceptable." This indicates that the web system is highly efficient in terms of time behavior and resource utilization, while also being effective in achieving its objectives. Overall, the system's functionalities are efficient and effective, providing a positive user experience.

Table 5 reveals the evaluation of the web system's maintainability. Based on the end users' evaluation, the Property Management Catalogue has received a Highly Acceptable rating in terms of Maintainability, with an overall average rating of 1.44. The respondents found the system's changeability to be clear and error-free, while the web system also provides prompt messages for input errors or after sending the requisition slip. The system's testability was found to be Very Acceptable, with respondents reporting no bugs or issues during testing, resulting in a positive feedback from users.

Table 5. Evaluation of the web system's maintainability

End Users (n=40)			Expert Users (n=10)		
Maintainability	Mean	Remarks	Maintainability	Mean	Remarks
Changeability. The changes of items and prices are noticeable and clear.	1.53	Very Acceptable	Changeability. The web system is able to update items, prices, and quantity stocks without errors.	1.25	Highly Acceptable
Analyzability. The web system shows confirmation after sending the requisition slips.	1.41	Highly Acceptable	Analyzability. The web system shows the messages after sending requisition slips.	1.33	Highly Acceptable
Testability. The web system does not reproduce issues during testing.	1.53	Very Acceptable	Testability. The web systems features and functionalities perform well during testing.	1.33	Highly Acceptable
Overall Average	1.49	Highly Acceptable		1.30	Highly Acceptable

The expert-users' evaluation of the application's maintainability received a highly acceptable rating of 1.30. Based on the table that the respondents have evaluated the Maintainability aspect of a web system, the first criterion, changeability, assesses how well the web system is able to update the list of items, prices, and quantity stocks without errors. The table indicates that the system is able to make these updates without errors, resulting in a score of 1.25, which is rated as "Highly Acceptable." The second criterion, analyzability, evaluates whether the web system shows prompt messages after sending requisition slips. The table states that the system displays messages promptly, resulting in a score of 1.33, which is also rated as "Highly Acceptable." The third criterion, testability, assesses how well the web system's features and functionalities perform during testing. The table indicates that the system performs well during testing, with a score of 1.33, which is again rated as "Highly Acceptable". Finally, the overall Average score is 1.3, which is also rated as "Highly Acceptable." This indicates that the web system is well-maintained and performs well in terms of changeability, analyzability, and testability. Overall, the system is reliable and can be updated and tested without errors, resulting in a positive user experience.

Table 6. Evaluation of the web system's portability

End Users (n=40)			Expert Users (n=10)		
Portability	Mean	Remarks	Portability	Mean	Remarks
Adaptability. The web system is able to run using different browsers.	1.53	Very Acceptable	Adaptability. The web system able to run properly on browsers (e.g., Google Chrome, Microsoft Edge).	1.25	Highly Acceptable
Portability. The web system is capable with the rest of the modules.	1.35	Highly Acceptable	Portability. The web system runs well with the rest when performing actions.	1.16	Highly Acceptable
Co-existence. The web system can be used in clients and browsers simultaneously.	1.43	Highly Acceptable	Co-existence. The web system has the capacity to be accessed by numerous clients and web browsers simultaneously.	1.50	Very Acceptable
Overall Average	1.44	Highly Acceptable		1.30	Highly Acceptable

Table 6 reveals the evaluation of the web system's portability. Based on the end users' evaluation of the material requisition system, the system has achieved a high level of satisfaction in terms of its portability with 1.44. The system's adaptability to different browsers and devices is very acceptable and has no compatibility issues. The web system is capable of communicating with other modules and services, such as sending MRS and Requisition Status. Additionally, the system has the capacity to be accessed by numerous clients and web browsers simultaneously without any failure, which indicates a highly acceptable co-existence.

Based on the experts' evaluation of the material requisition system, the first criterion, Adaptability, indicates that the system is able to run properly on these browsers, resulting in a score of 1.25, which is rated as "Highly Acceptable." The second criterion, Portability, indicates that the system runs well with the rest of the modules, resulting in a score of 1.16, which is also rated as "Highly Acceptable." The third criterion, Co-existence, states that the system has the capacity to be accessed by numerous clients and web browsers simultaneously, resulting in a score of 1.50, which is rated as "Very Acceptable." Finally, the overall average score is 1.3, which is rated as "Highly Acceptable." This indicates that the web system is highly portable and can run well on multiple computer browsers.

Table 7. Overall Level of Satisfaction

Category	Respondents	Remarks
Functionality	1.44	Highly Acceptable
Usability	1.46	Highly Acceptable
Efficiency	1.48	Highly Acceptable
Maintainability	1.49	Highly Acceptable
Portability	1.49	Highly Acceptable
Overall Average	1.48	Highly Acceptable

The data presented in Table 7 shows the overall average rating for end-users and expert users suggests that the application is highly acceptable. The respondents evaluated the material requisition system on the client side and have given a high level of satisfaction in all aspects evaluated, ranging from “Highly Acceptable” to “Very Acceptable”. The overall average score of 1.48 indicates that the system meets the clients’ expectations and that they are satisfied with the system’s functionality, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability. It can be concluded that the property management catalogue meets the clients’ requirements and expectations, and it can be considered a success.

However, it is still important to continue monitoring and improving the system to ensure its continued success and user satisfaction. Developers can use this feedback to continue to improve the application, ensuring that it remains effective and efficient for all users and follow the recommendations and suggestions of some respondents. Overall, the data suggests that the application is a success, and both end-users and experts are highly satisfied with its performance.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The web-based property management catalogue in the study is a web-based application that enables property management officers, department clients, and budget officer to manage the flow of unused materials within an organization. The features are ensured to fit the needs of the clients and SDCA staff, as it also gives a friendly user material procurement module for requesting and approving inventory goods.

The design and development of the material requisition slip module allows department clients to create material requisition slips for the materials they require, which are reviewed and approved by the Property Management Officer. The Inventory Management module keeps track of the inventory levels of the materials in the system, and the Issuance Workflow Management module facilitates the approval process for material requests and the subsequent issuance of materials to the requesting departments. The Reporting module generates reports on the inventory levels of materials, the issuance of materials, and the status of requisition slips, which the Budget Officer uses to monitor the use of materials and ensure that department budgets are not exceeded. The system is usable and can perform well, but more improvements should be able to give more satisfaction to the client’s needs.

Implementing and maintaining the system is crucial to ensuring that it meets the needs of the PMO, budget officer and department staff. The implementations of features to the system is proper and in accordance with their standards and expectations. It also creates a delay-free operation and manage inventory records to ensure resource availability. Overall, the web-based property management catalogue provides an efficient and streamlined way for organizations to manage and track the flow of materials in and out of their inventory. By using this system, organizations can ensure that they have the necessary materials on hand when needed, reduce waste and excess inventory, and make better-informed decisions about future material needs. Finally, the study recommends evaluating system functionality, security, and scalability, and assessing the impact on institutional performance in terms of inventory data accuracy, procurement costs, and user satisfaction. This will help organizations identify areas for improvement and ensure that the inventory management system continues to meet their needs over time.

As for the future researchers, it is important to evaluate the impact of any new features that will be added to the Material Requisition System. This could involve conducting tests to measure the impact on efficiency, user satisfaction, or other key performance indicators. This will help ensure that any changes made to the system are effective and useful. They should explore the additions of new features to the Material Requisition System, such as integration with assets tracking and management for Property Management Officers, to provide a more comprehensive materials management system for property management catalogue. Additionally, they could enhance the existing automatic notification system for inventory levels to also notify purchasing managers when inventory levels are low and trigger the procurement process. This could improve the efficiency of the system and help organizations maintain optimal inventory levels. As for the future of the web system, it is important to consider the needs of the

system's users. Conducting user studies and feedback sessions can help identify the specific requirements and challenges of each user group and help you design a more user-friendly system that meets their needs. When adding new features, it is important to ensure that the Material Requisition System remains secure. This could involve implementing access controls, encryption, and other security measures to protect the system from unauthorized access or data breaches. It is important to test them thoroughly and iterate them based on user feedback and performance metrics. This will help you identify any issues or bugs in the system and ensure that it continues to function smoothly over time.

References

- Afolabi, A., Abraham, Y., Ojelabi, R., & Awosika, O. (2020). Automation of the requisition process in material supply chain of construction firms. In S. K. Bhatia, S. Tiwari, S. Ruidan, M. C. Trivedi, & K. K. Mishra (Eds.), *Advances in computer, communication and computational sciences: Proceedings of IC4S 2019* (pp. 315-323). Springer Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-15-4409-5_28
- de Vicente Mohino, J., Bermejo Higuera, J., Bermejo Higuera, J. R., & Sicilia Montalvo, J. A. (2019). The application of a new secure software development life cycle (S-SDLC) with agile methodologies. *Electronics*, 8(11), 1218. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics8111218>
- Edeki, C. (2015). Agile software development methodology. *European Journal of Mathematics and Computer Science*, 2(1), 22-27. <https://www.idpublications.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/05/Agile-Software-Development-Methodology.pdf>
- Gao, D., Wang, N., Jiang, Q., & Jiang, B. (2022). *Enterprises' green growth model and value chain reconstruction: Theory and method*. Springer Nature Singapore. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-3991-4>
- Jenkins, A. (2021). *What is inventory? Types, examples and analysis*. Oracle NetSuite. <https://www.netsuite.com/portal/resource/articles/inventory-management/inventory.shtml>
- Oluwole, A. (2019). *Design and implementation of a computerized stock management system (a case study of Mide Supermarket)* [Unpublished manuscript]. https://www.academia.edu/40401229/DESIGN_AND_IMPLEMENTATION_OF_A_COMPUTERIZED_STOCK_MANAGEMENT_SYSTEM_A_CASE_STUDY_OF_MIDE_SUPERMARKET
- Singh, A. P. A., & Abhinav Parashar, A. (2021). Streamlining purchase requisitions and orders: A guide to effective goods receipt management. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research (JETIR)*, 8(5), g179-g184. <https://www.jetir.org/papers/JETIR2105952.pdf>
- Soegoto, E. S., & Palalungan, A. F. (2020). Web based online inventory information system. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 879(1), 012125. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/879/1/012125>
- Stackify Team. (2020). *What is SDLC? Understand the software development life cycle*. Stackify. <https://stackify.com/what-is-sdlc>
- Syed, S. A. (2021). Smart inventory management systems using RFID and IoT technologies for real-time stock visibility. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence Engineering and Transformation*, 2(1), 22-36. <https://doi.org/10.54660/IJAJET.2021.2.1.22-36>
- Utami, N., & Yulianto, H. D. (2019). Significant influence of information technology on the use of modern accounting software. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 662(2), 022003. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/662/2/022003>
- Wilson, B. (2022, November 11). *Agile methodology: What is agile model in software testing?* Medium. <https://bethwilsonuk.medium.com/agile-methodology-what-is-agile-model-in-software-testing-bc04b09bc161>